

A REPLACEMENT DESIGN FOR A STRUCTURAL WING BOX

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A design study of the structural wing box of a high performance V/STOL fighter configuration has been conducted, which considered several construction concepts and materials. The design concept selected for experimental confirmation was a replacement design utilizing a discretely-stiffened-sheet skin of graphite/epoxy bolted to aluminum substructure. This design was selected as optimum for the real constraints of the application at hand. The design was exercised in an experimental program which demonstrated that the concept was easily manufactured, could carry the design loads, could contain fuel and would save significant weight compared to the aluminum design.

Introduction

The design of structures utilizing high strength and stiffness fibrous composite materials has been studied and discussed at length during the past decade. As a result of these studies certain design precepts have become widely accepted as fundamental to efficient and reasonable design practice using these materials. These precepts include some or all of the following philosophies.

- (1) Composite designs should be all (or virtually all) composite material; mixing metallic and composite elements is bad practice.

- (2) To attain efficient and cost effective applications, the vehicle should have its configuration tailored to composite construction, i.e., replacement designs are rarely attractive.
- (3) Attachments and load introduction and removal from composite structure should be done using bonded joints; bolted joints are so inefficient in composite materials as to be impractical.
- (4) Sandwich construction is the desirable approach with composites whenever reasonably feasible.
- (5) The ply orientation selection should be optimized using sophisticated analysis and design tools. This optimization is necessary to obtain reasonable weight-savings with these materials.

Although each of the above philosophies has merit in certain applications, the author contends that the philosophies have become more widely preached and accepted than actual experience warrants. In this paper a specific design application will be considered--a high performance, military aircraft wing structure. The design solution selected is efficient in terms of weight savings, is believed to be producible at low cost and has been successfully demonstrated with experimental hardware. This design solution, however, mixes metallic substructure with composite skins, is a replacement design, uses all bolted attachments for load introduction, utilizes integrally-stiffened-skin construction and has a quasi-isotropic skin lay-up, i.e., this design does not fit any of the cited precepts.

The Design Study

The subject for this study was the Convair Model 200 V/STOL Fighter Attack Aircraft, which is a lift plus lift cruise V/STOL configuration designed for deck launched intercept, air-to-air and air-to-surface attack capability from the U.S. Navy's sea control ship concept. The Convair Division of General Dynamics has studied this configuration in depth, and the particular point design configuration considered for the composite study was well developed with respect to the metal configuration or baseline. V/STOL aircraft are, of course, uniquely sensitive to variations in structural weight, which led to detailed consideration of the possibility of using composite materials in the structure. However, cost is of ever-increasing concern and importance in aircraft production and purchase, so any potential weight reductions must be viewed in terms of the cost impact, as well as any additional risk factors.

The Model 200 wing is a 60-degree delta with integral fuel tanks in the structural box. Provisions are made on the wing for attaching the main landing gear and an external fuel tank. Wing attachment to the fuselage is accomplished by bolting the wing to six fuselage frames. The leading edge and tip of the wing are separate structures bolted to the structural box (these structures' effects were included in this study, but they were not included in the design tradeoff).

The wing structural concept utilizes multiple parallel spars. The spars are located at each of the fuselage attachments to provide discrete load paths for concentrated load introduction into the fuselage. The spars also carry spanwise shear, and separate the box into fuel cells. Ribs are required at the wing root, tip, main gear attachment, fuel tank pylon attachment and each side of the wheel well. This structural approach results in a grid of spanwise spar beams and chordwise rib beams. These members cannot be eliminated due to the cited load introduction and interface requirements.

The cover material must carry inplane shear and axial load, contain the fuel and resist the fuel pressures. The baseline metal design features integrally machined spanwise-tee-stiffened aluminum skins. The configuration has individual skin panels between spars (spliced at the spars) for ease of panel manufacture, maintenance and repair.

The design requirements for the wing are symmetrical load factors of +7.5g's and -2.5g's (limit), with maximum surface temperatures of 280^o, and internal maximum fuel pressures of 18 psi. A detailed finite element model of the wing was utilized for internal loads analysis and the subsequent flutter check. The primary loads on the wing produce small loads in the wing covers. Axial skin loads vary up to a maximum of 2,500 lbs/in tension, and 2000 lbs/in compression, with a maximum shear flow of less than 1400 lbs/in. Skin panel bending moments were based upon beaming the fuel pressures between the primary ribs, and are in general less than 500 in-lb/in.

The composite design was pursued seeking attractive weight savings at an attractive cost, and in a manner that would be acceptable to the buyer and user of such an airplane in the late 1970s. Low cost usually results when the design and manufacturing approach selected is simple, and thus simplicity was stressed. Acceptance by a potential user is easiest to obtain if the design is as little different from previous successful ones as possible. Acceptance is further encouraged if a recovery approach (in the event of subsequent manufacturing, cost or operational problems) is built into the design. In our situation, these considerations pointed to a replacement design assembled similarly (or identically) to the metal design, such that subsequent problems could,

if necessary, be solved by reverting to the metal wing. Furthermore, these considerations suggested that other functional requirements, such as fuel sealing and access, be accomplished using conventional techniques.

The author contends that such "restrictions" on composite designs are pragmatic restraints that will exist until many more years of practical experience is gathered with composite materials. As such, the problem to be addressed is finding design solutions that are sufficiently attractive in terms of weight saved and cost within these constraints, rather than finding "more optimized" solutions which violate these constraints and thus are unacceptable to the purchasers.

Several composite wing concepts were considered, including combinations of graphite-epoxy skins, spars and ribs, aluminum spars, aluminum ribs, boron/aluminum skins and ribs, and boron/epoxy skins. As a first step, the weight summary for the metal wing was examined. This revealed that the skins represented 47 percent of the total wing box weight, the spars represented 30 percent and the ribs 8 percent. Since the skins represented the largest potential weight reduction and appeared to have the least problems relative to load introduction, they were studied in the most detail.

The concepts considered for the skins included spanwise blade-stiffened graphite/epoxy, boron/aluminum and boron/epoxy skins, I-stiffened graphite/epoxy skins, graphite/epoxy sandwich skins, and both tee and blade stiffened aluminum. Closed sections were not considered to avoid fuel volume losses and inspection problems, and because secondary joining operations could be eliminated with our graphite-epoxy manufacturing approach if open sections were utilized. Critical loads on the cover material are spanwise compression and internal fuel pressure. The tension and shear loads are of only secondary importance for the design concepts considered. The basic skin thickness was limited by individual ply thickness and the necessity of maintaining mid-plane symmetry. The ply orientation was determined by fuel pressure bending. The ply orientation utilized were 0 ± 60 for the graphite/epoxy and boron/epoxy designs, and 0 ± 45 for the boron/aluminum design. These orientations were selected based upon a complex combination of manufacturing considerations such as minimum ply module constraints (such that edge buildups could be simply incorporated while maintaining symmetry), stringer spacing considerations, and the restriction to laminate families have a reasonably wide experience base. The discrete stiffeners in graphite/ and boron/epoxy were selected to be 0 ± 45 degrees based on the combination of buckling and strength requirements, and 0 degrees in boron/aluminum (acceptable because of the higher transverse stiffness and strength of

boron/aluminum). The periphery of each panel and the rib attachment region was made a constant (greater) thickness for use with standard countersunk fasteners.

Within the orientation constraints described above, the design concepts were optimized for different values of spanwise compression. These results are shown graphically in Figure 1, a plot of spanwise compression, N_x , versus a measure of weight efficiency, $\bar{t}\rho$. As the figure indicates, all of the composite designs are more efficient than the aluminum designs. The boron/aluminum design is among the most efficient concepts for larger values of inplane compressions (3 to 4 kips/in), but minimum gage limitations using the large diameter (5.6 mil) boron fibers result in less efficiency at the loads encountered in the present application. The graphite/epoxy sandwich design is slightly better than the I-stiffened graphite/epoxy design at the load levels of interest; however, this small advantage is reversed when edge attachment weights are included. The sandwich design also utilizes very thin six ply skins (.030 inches), which pose some handling and fuel containment concerns, and the sandwich skin also takes up needed fuel volume. The blade stiffened graphite/epoxy design is, as expected, slightly less efficient than the I-stiffened design due to the decreased bending efficiency of this section. And, also as expected, the lower specific stiffness boron/epoxy design is less efficient than the corresponding graphite/epoxy design.

Graphite/epoxy ribs and spars, and boron/aluminum ribs and spars, have also been designed. The ribs are straightforward all-composite designs with sealing grooves for fuel sealing. The spars are also straightforward except for transition regions for attachment to the fuselage. In the graphite/epoxy design, the spars have integrally bonded titanium root fittings, while in the boron/aluminum design an aluminum root fitting is utilized, mechanically fastened to the outer boron/aluminum spar.

The weights of the various wings studied are tabulated in Table I. Each of the graphite/epoxy wing skins include a weight increment for aluminum screen mesh molded into the outer surface for lightning protection, as well as an allowance for corrosion protection of all parts (graphite-epoxy does not normally corrode, but attached aluminum parts must be thoroughly separated from the graphite/epoxy parts.)

As Table I indicates, the graphite/epoxy sandwich design is less attractive than the integrally stiffened design in this application. Less weight is saved, the resulting design has higher technical risk due to its frailty, and the manufacturing complexity is greater.

The boron aluminum design is less efficient than the graphite/epoxy designs, although it still presents attractive weight savings. In light of the present material costs and the much smaller experience base with this material this design was dropped in favor of the graphite/epoxy designs.

Also as indicated in Table I, the "total graphite/epoxy" design shows the maximum weight saving, an attractive 27.7 percent. However, the highest risk structure of this wing, the spars (due to the bonded titanium joint design with high load transfer), save only 3.5 percent of the wing weight. Furthermore, the ribs save only 2.2 percent. The graphite/epoxy skin substitution saves 22 percent. The configuration of graphite/epoxy skins on aluminum substructure avoids all of the technical problems related to high load transfer to the fuselage, and also have the advantage that the composite parts of this configuration are exposed to the outside, and can be easily removed. Furthermore, the skins of a wing such as the one under study are a small part of the total cost of the wing. As a result, even if the composite wing skins should be more expensive than the aluminum wing skins, this substitution will show a large percent weight saving at a probably small increase in percent cost.

As a result of the above considerations, the graphite/epoxy I-stiffened skin bolted to aluminum spars and ribs was selected for more detailed analysis and experimental demonstration. A thermal analysis was performed to determine the compatibility of the skin to the substructure. The analysis assumed aerodynamic heating during a supersonic dash. These temperatures were used to predict the strain due to mismatch in expansion coefficients, which in turn was combined with the mechanical strains and compared to the allowable strain of the material at that temperature. No problems were identified. A subsonic strip theory flutter analysis was also performed on the wing which showed the wing possesses an adequate flutter margin.

The Experimental Verification

The objectives of this experimental program were to demonstrate that the integrally I-stiffened wing skin panels could be efficiently fabricated, that the design incorporating these skins on aluminum substructure was capable of carrying the design loads, and that the mechanical attachment and sealing system selected were acceptable.

The specimen selected for detailed design, fabrication and test is illustrated in Figure 2. This specimen was ten feet long, three feet wide and 7.3 inches deep. The test section was made up of the four foot center section of the specimen, with closing longitudinal aluminum spars that span the entire specimen length

and three aluminum ribs across the test panel. The covers of the non-test section of the specimen were 5/16 aluminum plate. The upper panel was designed utilizing representative Model 200 wing loads, primarily compression. The lower panel was designed to pattern the upper panel except it was made thicker and incorporates access provisions. The aluminum substructure was designed to distribute the desired loads uniformly to the upper panel and to facilitate fuel pressure cycling.

The upper panel was the primary focus of the design and test since it represents the critical conditions of the wing design (compression and fuel pressure containment). This three-foot by four-foot panel consisted of a .06-inch skin (12 plies of Hercules A-S/3501 graphite/epoxy) stepwise thickened to .24 inches (in steps of .06) and stiffened with nine I-cross-section longitudinal stiffeners. The 12-ply module that forms the basic skin are all identical and are symmetrical within themselves. This allows the modules to be layed up and cut regardless of which side is "up". The stiffeners were spaced at 3.5 inches and sized to prevent the skin from buckling below limit load. The resulting stiffeners were as pictured in Figure 3. These stiffeners were stepped in height to match the panel buildups at the edges. The ends of the stiffeners were locally built up to accommodate aluminum shear clips which tied the stiffeners to the ribs. Aluminum screen mesh was incorporated in the skin surface per the wing skin design for lightning strike.

The lower panel design was identical to the upper panel except for the addition of a 12-ply module to the entire panel and the addition of two circular access doors. The substructure was integrally machined 2024-T351 aluminum. The assembly of the substructure and of the graphite/epoxy parts to the substructure was by standard mechanical fasteners, i.e., Huckbolt and Huckrimp titanium fasteners. Fuel sealing was accomplished utilizing grooves on the substructure facings and faying surface sealants (a polysulfide sealant in this case).

The upper and lower panels were each manufactured using a thermal-pressure forming process. The panels were each formed in a single curing process as integral net panels, following the steps listed below:

- (1) A model of the panel base (with square sections replacing the stiffeners) was made of aluminum with wood stiffeners and a rubber cast around this model. The resulting silicone rubber tool is shown in Figure 4.
- (2) The skin was layed up in 12-ply plymodules and placed on the aluminum baseplate, Figure 5.

- (3) The stiffeners were layed up as flat plymodules, then wrapped around aluminum stiffener forming mandrels, Figure 6.
- (4) The stiffeners were inserted into the rubber tool "upside down", Figure 7.
- (5) The base skin was placed on top of the rubber tool, Figure 8, and the tool closed with a flat baseplate.
- (6) The panel and tool assembly was placed in a heated press and cured. Removal from the tool provided a net integrally stiffened panel.

The wing box test specimen has been tested through seven loading tests and four fuel tank pressure tests (with one of the loading tests performed with fuel tank pressure) as planned. The test set-up is shown in Figure 9, and the tests conducted are summarized in Table II. The test section was instrumented with 95 strain gages, which were read at ten percent loading increments during the tests.

Analysis of the test results indicated that the load distributions were uniform, and that the load-strain relationships were linear up to ultimate design loads. The specimen carried all of the design loads including the cyclic pressure loadings with no signs of distress or noises. Little change in strain distribution was noted when the end clips were removed. The test box did not leak. In short, the test specimen confirmed the integrity of the design and manufacturing process.

Conclusions

A design study of the use of composites in the structural wing box of a high performance fighter configuration has been conducted. The study was constrained by the "real world" need to sell the resulting composite design to the potential purchaser and user. This constraint required a design with a recovery approach available in the event of subsequent manufacturing, cost or operational problems, and suggested the use of conventional approaches to functional requirements such as fuel sealing and access. Furthermore, a reasonable weight savings at low or no additional cost was needed. These constraints were successfully met with a replacement design utilizing integrally I-stiffened graphite/epoxy skins bolted to aluminum spars and ribs. The resulting design concept has been experimentally confirmed with a large test box, which confirmed that the concept was easily manufactured, could carry the design loads, could keep the fuel contained, and would save significant weight compared to the aluminum design.

TABLE I

Wing Box Weight Summary

Component	Aluminum	G/E Skins, Ribs, Spars		G/E Skins and Ribs		G/E Skins		G/E Sandwich		Boron Aluminum	
	Baseline Wt Lbs	Wt Lbs	% Saved	Wt Lbs	% Saved	Wt Lbs	% Saved	Wt Lbs	% Saved	Wt Lbs	% Saved
Skins	512.6	329.8	35.7	329.8	35.7	329.8	35.7	383.0	25.3	367.8	23.2
Ribs	96.0	73.6	23.3	73.6	23.3	96.0	-	73.6	23.0	75.4	21.5
Spars	324.2	288.0	11.2	324.2	-	324.2	-	288.0	11.2	324.2	-
Sub-Total	932.8	691.7		727.6		750.0		744.6		767.4	
Structural Increments Added	148.0	90.2		91.0		91.0		90.2		99.6	
Total Wing Weight	1080.8	781.6	27.7	818.6	24.2	841.0	22.0	834.8	22.4	867.0	20.0

TABLE II

Summary of Testing Performed on Wing Box Test Specimen

Test No.	Type of Test	Tank Fluid
1	90 Percent Ultimate Bending, 0 Pressure	Freon
2	90 Percent Ultimate Bending plus Torsion, 0 Pressure	Freon
3	67 Percent Ultimate Bending plus Torsion, 16.2 psi Pressure	Freon
4	100 Percent Ultimate Bending plus Torsion, 0 Pressure	Freon
5	1790 Pressure Cycles to 12 psi	Freon
6	Leak Check, 72 Hours at 2 psi	Jet Fuel
7	4000 Pressure Cycles to 20 psi	Jet Fuel
8	100 Percent Ultimate Torsion, 0 Pressure	Air
9	100 Percent Ultimate Bending, 0 Pressure	Air
10	100 Percent Ultimate Bending plus Torsion, 0 Pressure End Clips Removed	Air
11	25 psi Pressure, End Clips Removed	Freon

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Figure 1 Relative Compression Efficiency of Various Wing Cover Concepts

Figure 2 Test Specimen Selected for Experimental Verification

Figure 3 Cross-Section of Typical I-Section Integral Stiffener

Figure 4 Cast Silicone Rubber Tool

Figure 5 Panel Skin (Prebled Plymodules)

Figure 6 Mated Aluminum Stiffener Forming Mandrels with Graphite/Epoxy in Place

Figure 7 Installation of Stiffeners into Silicone Tool

Figure 8 Installation of Skin onto Silicone Tool

Figure 9 Test Specimen in Test Fixture

RAPPORTEUR'S REPORT

DESIGNING FOR STRUCTURAL APPLICATIONS 1975 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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The design of composites to carry load requires some form of stress analysis from which deformation, strength and life expectancy can be estimated. The papers in this section are concerned primarily with deformation, including buckling, and strength of various composites, but not concerned with life.

It is useful to classify the gross behavior and methods of stress analysis of plane (two-dimensional) composites so as to guide us in the discussion of some of the papers in this section. Composites on the microscopic or local level are always heterogeneous and isotropic, with the exception of graphite fiber which is anisotropic due to its crystalline structure. On the macroscopic or gross level, composites can have four levels of anisotropy as indicated in Table I. The stress-strain relation needed for stress analysis must be adjusted to reflect the anisotropy by using the appropriate number of constants. The number of parameters for strength of composites will increase with the complexity of composites as we move down in Table I. The point of Table I is that stress analysis results are dependent on material properties and boundary conditions. Only when a material is isotropic, is the stress distribution independent of material properties under plane conditions. So as materials become more complex, the required stress analyses also become more complex. In fact, composites are specialized structures rather than plain materials. The estimate of deformation and strength, and the associated mechanisms on the local level requires highly disciplined approaches. There is no simple, direct formula for such estimates such as the rule-of-mixtures equation, in general.

In Table II, various methods of stress analysis are broadly

classified in terms of theoretical approaches and number of dimensions. Both elasticity and strength of materials are disciplined in the sense that assumptions and limitations can be explicitly stated, although the effect of assumptions made in strength of materials is not always clear. Thus, elasticity can be termed exact; the strength of materials, approximate. The extent of anisotropy as those listed in Table I can be systematically accounted for in these disciplined approaches; for example, the anisotropic constants appear as coefficients in the partial differential equations of equilibrium. The same cannot be said for the approaches listed under "others" in Table II. Netting analysis for example is intended to relate strength of fibers directly to that of a composite pressure vessel with the aid of equilibrium or balance of forces. No consideration is given to deformation and strain compatibility in this approach. This omission is not permitted in the disciplined approaches. The shear-lag and pull-out analyses are also based on the balance of forces which is a necessary but not sufficient condition for stress analysis. In Table II disciplined approaches are replaced by questionable estimates as we move down. Once again we should recognize that composites are not simple materials but parts of a complex structure.

Oversimplifications of stress or strength estimates have led and will continue to lead to erroneous conclusions. Utility of an "engineering" solution offers no ground to be undisciplined. Objectivity and rigor are not to be compromised. Modern computers have made many approximate estimates obsolete. This does not mean that simple formulas are not needed. They are indeed very essential but should be checked against more exact solutions in order to determine their bounds of applicability. Without guidelines from the theory of elasticity it is not always possible to estimate a priori which of the six stress components are dominant or negligible. Interlaminar stresses for example often defy intuition. Complex stress states are always present in composites, and are dependent on the stress-strain relations and boundary conditions. For this reason, there is no general solution to the shear-lag or pull-out problem without the full specification of the material properties, geometry and loading conditions. All too often, popular concepts of composites have been developed without the benefit of accurate stress analysis. The critical length for short fiber composites is a questionable concept for the translation of stiffness and strength, and cannot be examined until disciplined analysis is applied.

In elasticity solutions of composite materials, the local variation of stresses as we traverse from one constituent phase to another is illustrated by Rybicki and Pagano. The validity of macroscopic descriptions of a locally heterogeneous body as represented by effective moduli can be checked against the actual oscillation of the local stresses. Papers by Kafka, and Chesquiere and Bauwens also dealt with composites as materials with microstructures. But

both papers are in an early stage of development. More work is necessary before new and definitive results can be presented.

In the theory of plates and shells, several papers are included. An example of outstanding work for the purpose of designing a real structure is presented by Corvelli et al. Careful analysis and test correlation were presented in a systematic and concise manner. It is gratifying to know that a high degree of confidence in design of composite structure does exist at selected locations. Ishai and Saggi presented data on buckling of one dimensional structural members and compared with classical buckling solutions. This is also a confidence building exercise which is so essential for users of composites to convince themselves. Post buckling of plates has not been treated extensively in the literature. Banks' work is therefore a welcome addition. Jones and Morgans' work on buckling of shells with materials with different tensile and compressive moduli has also been treated in a very limited scope in the literature because most advanced composites now in use do not have different tensile and compressive moduli. The formulation of the problem is quite difficult in the neighborhood of zero stress or strain where a discontinuity in the slope of the stress-strain curve occurs. The problem is further complicated when such behavior under multi-axial stresses in an anisotropic body is to be incorporated.

Examples of netting analysis can be found in papers by Moore, and Hardwick. This approximate approach intended exclusively for pressure vessels is not a reliable substitute for conventional structural analysis. Beyond the fact that composite performance is highly dependent on the ply or laminate thickness, elasticity and the theory of shells are the only self-consistent theories to predict deformation and are far superior to netting analysis. A bad analysis may turn out to be worse than no analysis at all. Other papers that relied on approximate analysis included that by Beese using rule of mixtures, and that by Greenwood and Rose using what appears to be an unorthodox method of stress analysis. It is believed that these problems are solvable within the realm of the classical mechanics of solids, pioneered by numerous European and Russian scholars since the early 19th century.

There were papers without analysis of any kind. There were no theoretical predictions as to what we might expect--the punch line? Some had neither theory nor data - a purely philosophical treatise - which should not have been assigned to a session devoted to "Designing for Structural Applications."

Mechanics of composites will continue to provide the methodology and data for design of structures. Composites offer unusual properties not available in conventional structural materials. Filamentary laminates in particular have shown high fatigue resistance, insensitivity to stress concentrations, and high durability against hostile environments. As manufacturing methods and cost continue

to improve, composites will replace many existing materials and create new applications with or without accurate stress analysis. It behooves us to provide the most effective stress analysis to support the design of composites for structural applications.

TABLE I GROSS BEHAVIOR OF PLANE COMPOSITES

LEVEL OF ANISOTROPY	NUMBER OF CONSTANTS	EXAMPLES
Isotropy	2	Random fiber composites Particulate composites π/n laminates ($n=3, 4, \dots$)
Square-Symmetry	3	Special cross-ply $[0, 90]$ angle-ply $[\pm 45]$ laminates
Orthotropy	4	Unidirectional composites General cross-ply $[0_p, 90_q]$ and angle-ply $[\pm \theta]$ laminates, and their combinations $[0_p, 90_q, \pm \theta_r]$, ($p, q, r = 1, 2, \dots$)
Anisotropy	6	General laminates (nonorthotropy)

TABLE II STRESS ANALYSIS OF PLANE COMPOSITES

DIMENSIONS THEORY	2 - D	1 - D
Elasticity	Plane Elasticity	Special Case of 2 - D
Strength of Materials	Plates & Shells	Bars & Beams
Others	--	Netting Analysis Shear-lag Pull-out